

Sensitivity and Parameter Analysis of Population Balance Applied to Non-Reactive Gas-Liquid Semi-Batch Stirred Tanks

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Abstract

This work applies the multifluid population balance model (MPB) to a non-reactive gas-liquid semi-batch stirred tank reactor (STR) to describe the bubble size distribution and the interfacial area density. A robust numerical solution method for solving the population balance equation is essential for large parameter studies. We compare and evaluate three numerical methods from literature and a novel method developed in this work using on analytical solutions of known test cases. While no method clearly outperforms others, the finite volume method with Gauss quadrature, proposed by us, demonstrates fast, robust, and precise results. To demonstrate the robustness and to investigate the STR, a large sensitivity and parameter study is carried out in which several parameters of the model are varied in a one-at-a-time analysis. The studies reveal strong dependencies on kernel parameters and process conditions. Our findings confirm trends from literature and highlight the importance of understanding the complex interaction of breakage and coalescence. Furthermore, we fitted the model parameters to experimental data in a preliminary study, showing good agreement with measured data. The presented MPB, in conjunction with our novel solution methodology proved to be a valuable tool for investigating the intricate behavior of the dispersed gas phase within the STR. However, the model also demonstrated shortcomings, as it lacked the capacity to describe the gas holdup. The primary objective of future research will be to identify and develop modelling approaches that address this shortcoming.

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1. Introduction

In industrial production processes, the stirred tank reactor (STR) is a widely used standard reactor. It is ideal for performing chemical or biotechnological gas-liquid syntheses, such as fermentations [1, 2]. Model-based optimization and design of this type of reactor requires knowledge of the behavior of the dispersed gas phase (i.e., the bubbles) in the reactor. In particular, the total interfacial area is important because it directly affects the mass and heat transport between the gas and liquid phase. In addition, the residence time of the gas phase and gas holdup is needed to calculate conversions of gas phase reactions and the total level of aerated liquid in the reactor. Ultimately, these parameters depend on the size of the gas bubbles present in the reactor. This bubble size distribution (BSD) is influenced by several parameters, including the geometry of the reactor, the stirrer and the gas sparger, the physicochemical properties of the fluids, and the power input by the supplied gas flux and stirrer. The use of multiphase computational fluid dynamics to model these dependencies is time and resources consuming, especially when investigating large parameter spaces as it is necessary during process development and reactor design. Therefore, engineers often use a variety of correlations from the literature [3–11] to describe the influence of the property data, geometry and process conditions on the behavior of the process (e.g., mass and heat transfer, gas holdup) and to design STRs. The disadvantage of these correlations is that, for simplicity, they are often strongly empirical in nature and contain little physical knowledge. Thus, they can often only be used to describe the behavior of the STR within the range of conditions for which reliable experimental data exist, and not to extrapolate to new conditions. The enormous variation in the composition of the gas and liquid phases alone makes it almost impossible to predict the behavior of an unstudied chemical system on the basis of these correlation. In previous works, we presented a promising alternative to efficiently describe the behavior of the dispersed gas phase in reactors and to enable predictions outside the experimentally studied conditions [12, 13]. The approach uses a one-dimensional multifluid population balance model (MPB) and is a simplified version of Jakobsen and coworkers [14, 15] kinetic theory approach with size resolution (KTAWSR). In our previous work, we applied the MPB to predict the axial profile of the bubble size distribution, gas phase velocity, and gas volume fraction in a bubble column (non-reactive, semi-batch).

The MPB approach uses the most common simplifying assumptions to describe the internal flows in reactors, e.g. one-dimensional axial flow with no variation in radial direction and ideal mixed so that no spatial gradients occur. To describe the bubble columns, we used the first assumption [12, 13]. In this paper, we describe the stirred tank reactor as ideally mixed.

The characteristic of the KTAWSR is that all transport equation of the dispersed phase such as mass, species mass, momentum, and energy as well as their corresponding state variables mass, phase velocity, species concentration and temperature become functions of the bubble

diameter like the density function in the common population balance equation (PBE). This method enables the description of the influence of bubble breakage, coalescence, growth and nucleation on the interfacial area, the residence time of the bubbles in the reactor and the gas volume fraction. In our previous work [12, 13], we found that the simplifying assumptions made concerning the flow field in the reactor and the breakage and coalescence behavior of the bubbles necessitated the fitting of model parameters (the parameters of the breakage and coalescence kernel) to experimental data in order to describe the behavior of the dispersed phase in the bubble columns in an satisfying manner. The parameters utilized to describe breakage and coalescence were not determined through independent experiments; rather, they were fitted directly to the data from the bubble column. It is theoretically possible that the parameters are correlated. Furthermore, potential discrepancies in other submodels, such as the model describing the turbulent energy dissipation rate, may also be attributed to these parameters. Nevertheless, our findings demonstrate that despite the simplicity of the parameter estimation method, which involves only four fitting parameters, the model is capable of accurately predicting experimental results across a wide range of parameters, as evidenced by the findings of [13]. As a result, our methodology represents an optimal balance between prediction performance and the experimental and modeling effort required. The methodology can be used to rapidly assess the significant influence of reactor geometry, operating conditions, and chemical system properties on reactor behavior.

In this study, we employed this methodology to describe the behavior of the dispersed gas phase in stirred tank reactors. The gas feed is continuous while no in or out flow of liquid phase is considered (semi-batch mode). As previously stated, we assume that the reactor is ideally mixed, thus negating the occurrence of spatial gradients within the reactor. However, in contrast to our previous investigation, we consider here the transient behavior of the reactor. Consequently, the KTAWSR approach results in the properties of the dispersed phase becoming functions of the bubble diameter and time. Furthermore, we extended the PBE so that the influence of mass transfer between the phases on the BSD can be explicitly accounted for. In our recent publication [16], we presented a detailed discussion on the consideration of mass transfer in the PBE.

In order to facilitate rapid and comprehensive parameter studies with the MPB, it is essential to devise a rapid, straightforward, and, in particular, robust methodology for solving the governing equations. Given that the PBE represents a transient integro-partial differential equation, it is crucial to select and optimize the solver for the specific task at hand. Basically, there are two approaches for solving the PBE, one is to solve for moments of the density function and the other is to solve directly for the density function. Methods based on moments such as [17–20] are often used [21–25] as they are simple and efficient. The disadvantage, however, is that these methods are not very accurate and the density function can only be obtained by making further strong assumptions [26, 27]. As a result, important phenomena such as multimodal density functions and their effects on the system cannot be investigated. The methods that directly solve the density function can reproduce these phenomena, which is why this approach is further considered in this paper.

Numerous methods within this class are described in the literature [27–31]. One aim of the present work is to undertake a comparative evaluation of the performance of different solvers.

For that reason, we implemented and compared four different methods: 1) spectral orthogonal collocation method, which were developed by Jakobsen and coworker [28, 32] and used in our previous studies [12, 13], 2) the classical fixed pivot technique [33] as it used e.g. in OpenFOAM [29], 3) a meshless radial basis method [27] and 4) a finite volume method with Gauss quadrature which was developed in this work. The solution methods were selected on the basis of the availability of information in the literature and the simplicity of implementation. It should be noted that this article does not aim to provide a comprehensive mathematical review of solution methods (for which the reader is referred to [34, 35]). Instead, the objective is to identify a method that enables engineers to easily and quickly navigate the complex landscape of advanced multiphase modelling involving PBE. The performance of the different methodologies was evaluated by benchmarking the numerical solutions of four straightforward and renowned PBE problems against their analytical solutions that are documented in the literature [36–42].

The best numerical solution method, the method proposed by us, was used to solve the MPB of the STR. Given the model assumptions, it is not possible to determine the gas holdup in the reactor (see Section 3.1 for a detailed discussion). Therefore, the sensitivity and parameter analysis presented in this work is primarily intended to demonstrate the robustness of the numerical solution method. However, the trends found here, despite the artificial assumption of constant gas holdup, were compared with the corresponding trends from the literature, if available. In these parameter studies most parameters of the MPB were examined in a one-at-the-time analysis, e.g. the choice of the kernels and their parameters, as well as the influence of the process conditions, the design of the gas sparger and of the physicochemical properties of gas and liquid phase.

Despite the artificial constant gas holdup, most of the trends from the literature could be confirmed in the sensitivity and parameter analysis. But more important the results show that the solution method developed in this work is simple, fast and robust in comparison to the other methods investigated. For that reason, it is well suited for parameter studies in which the MPB must be solved for many different parameters.

Furthermore, the findings of a preliminary study are presented, wherein the parameters of the breakage and coalescence kernels were estimated through the utilisation of experimental measurements of the BSD in a STR. While the model is capable of reproducing the observed data, certain limitations are evident, which will be addressed in future studies.

In summary, this work illustrates the benefits of our MPB for the representation of multiphase STRs. The model is relatively inexpensive to compute, yet it can describe the interaction of different sub-processes, such as the breakage and coalescence of bubbles and mass transfer. This work represents a significant advancement in our efforts to develop a model that can adequately describe the complex behavior of a dispersed multiphase system in a STR, while requiring only a limited set of empirical equations and parameters.

2. Experimental Setup

The Fig. 2.1 illustrates the experimental setup used in this work. Compressed air from the utility supply was dispersed at the bottom of stainless steel vessel (1, the number refers to the Fig. 2.1) with a diameter of 0.3 m by a spider sparger (2) with a diameter of 0.15 m, four arms and six orifices per arm of 2 mm diameter each and exits the vessel at the top into the ambient.

Figure 2.1.: Schematic illustration of the experimental setup.

The air flux was controlled by a mass flow controller (3) of type GF040 (GF040CXXC-0008051L-N2AVS5-XXXXXX-00C) from the manufacture Brooks Instrument (Dresden, Germany).

The continuous liquid phase was a mixture consisting of osmosis water (conductivity about 1100 μS adjusted with Na_2SO_4) and $w_{c,\text{EtOH}} = 0.01 \text{ kg kg}^{-1}$ ethanol (EtOH). This mixture was pre-filled (about 27 L) and remains in the vessel during the experiment. The possibility of ethanol being stripped out during the experiment was negated by a preliminary simulation study.

The STR was agitated with two 6-blade Rushton turbines (4) driven by a Hei-TORQUE Ultimate 400 stirrer motor (5) from the manufacture Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG (Schwabach, Germany), which also measures the torque on the shaft. To intensify the mixing, the STR has four baffles (7) equidistantly distributed around the vessel.

The in-house developed optical multimode online probe (OMOP, 6) was used to determine the BSD [43, 44]. It records telecentric shadowgraph images of the bubbly flow in a measuring gap (4 mm). Then, an pre-trained convolutional neural network developed by Weibel *et al.* [45] automatically detects and evaluates the bubbles so that the BSD can be calculated. Details of the OMOP and evaluation procedure can be found elsewhere [13, 43–45]. The OMOP was located under the stirrer. In a preliminary study, it was found that the measured BSD to be independent of the measurement position, proving ideal mixed conditions. Further details of the geometry of the STR are summarized in the Supplementary Information Tab. S.6.

To carry out an experiment, the mixture was pre-filled, the stirrer was started and adjusted to the desired speed. As soon as the torque had stabilized, the gas was introduced, and simultaneously the measurement of the BSD was started. An experiment lasts 30 minutes, with an image being taken with the OMOP every second. The first 60 images were stacked to create the inlet BSD, and then subsequently every 120 images were stacked to create a BSD. The last BSD consists again only of 60 images to match the total number of recorded images (1800 pcs.). In summary, this results in 16 measured BSDs.

In the experiment, the mixture including the holdup, the gas flux including the gas type, the stirrer, the stirrer speed, the sparger and baffle plates can be varied. However, this work only serves as a preliminary study for a larger experimental study to be conducted in future to evaluate the prediction performance of the develop model, so only one experiment at $j_d = 0.6 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ and 300 RPM is considered here.

The measured BSDs are summarized in the Supplementary Material.

3. Modelling and Simulation

3.1. System Description and Assumptions

To investigate the transient behavior of the BSD within the STR, it is assumed that a single-component gas enters the vessel through a bottom sparger at a specified mass flow rate $\dot{m}_{d,in}$, characterized by an inlet bubble size distribution $f_{d,in}^m$, and exits from the top with a mass flow rate $\dot{m}_{d,out}$ and distribution f_d^m , based on the assumption of ideal mixing. The liquid phase is neither fed nor withdrawn from the reactor, constituting a semi-batch process. Phase mixing is facilitated by a stirrer, ensuring ideal mixing conditions for both liquid and gas phase. The system maintains constant pressure and temperature, treating the physicochemical properties of the fluids enclosed as constant. Entrainment of gas phase by the stirrer is neglected. Furthermore, it is assumed that the mass change of the liquid phase due to mass transfer between the liquid and gas phases is negligible compared to the total mass of the liquid phase. As a result, the total mass/volume and the composition of the liquid phase remains constant within the reactor, rendering a mass and species balance of the liquid phase unnecessary. Together with the single-component gas case, only the mass balance of the gas phase, the mass-based PBE, needs to be considered. It is important to note that in this work, mass transfer is considered directly in the mass-based PBE because it completely replaces the mass balance of the gas phase. This approach contrasts with the usual ad hoc solution, in which the PBE is solved in addition to the gas phase mass balance in the two-fluid model to obtain a better estimate of the interfacial area density or bubble diameter [23].

As previously stated, for engineers, knowledge of the residence time of the dispersed phase in the reactor is of significant importance. This information allows for the assessment of the conversion of reactants and the selectivity to target products in the reactor. In the bubble column, the residence time distribution as a function of the bubble diameter can be obtained from the axial phase velocity, which is determined from the momentum balance of the dispersed phase using the KTAWSR [13]. Given the assumption of ideal mixing in the reactor, a global momentum balance over the STR cannot yield information about the velocity of the gas phase. In order to obtain this information, it would be necessary to consider the internal flow conditions of the gas and liquid phases, which are also influenced by a number of factors, including the type and speed of the stirrer, the design of the gas sparger and other internals, such as baffles. The development of such a model was not within the scope of the present paper; however, it will be considered in future work. In this study, the residence time of the gas phase was fixed at a constant value to align with the experimentally correlated gas holdup in the reactor. It is acknowledged that this simplification is at odds with our general objective of developing a model approach that requires only a minimal number of measurement data from the considered process, thereby facilitating

process optimization and scale-up. Nevertheless, the objective of this paper is to develop and test a solution method for the MPB. In this context, this assumption is deemed acceptable.

As the gas holdup is set to a constant value, the overall volume of the enclosed fluids resp. the gasified volume is constant. Consequently, the mass flow rate of the gas phase exiting the reactor $\dot{m}_{d,out}$ is equal to the mass flow rate of the gas entering the reactor via the sparger $\dot{m}_{d,in}$ minus the mass flow rate due to phase change (see Supplementary Information S.3.1).

3.2. Governing Equations

If the assumptions and conditions from Section. 3.1 are applied to the rigorous KTAWSR of Vik *et al.* [14], it is reduced to solely a simplified form of the PBE Eq. (3.1). A derivation can be found in the Supplementary Information S.3.2.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\dot{m}_{d,out}}{V_R} \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\int_{\xi_{min}}^{\xi_{max}} f_d^m(\xi, t) d\xi} - \frac{\dot{m}_{d,in}}{V_R} \frac{f_{d,in}^m(\xi, t)}{\int_{\xi_{min}}^{\xi_{max}} f_{d,in}^m(\xi, t) d\xi} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_\xi(\xi, t) f_d^m(\xi, t)) \\ & = \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{V_d(\xi)} \frac{1}{\rho_d} \frac{dm_d}{dt} - B_D^m(\xi, t) + B_B^m(\xi, t) - C_D^m(\xi, t) + C_B^m(\xi, t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

In which the growth rate due to phase change, the breakage death and birth term as well as the coalescence death and birth term are:

$$v_\xi(\xi, t) = \frac{1}{\frac{\pi}{2} \xi^2 \rho_d} \frac{dm_d}{dt} \quad (3.2)$$

$$B_D^m(\xi, t) = H\left(\xi - \sqrt[3]{2\xi_{min}^3}\right) b(\xi) f_d^m(\xi, t) \quad (3.3)$$

$$B_B^m(\xi, t) = H\left(\sqrt[3]{\xi_{max}^3 - \xi_{min}^3} - \xi\right) \rho_d V_d(\xi) \int_{\xi}^{\xi_{max}} \nu P(\xi, \zeta) b(\zeta) \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, t)}{\rho_d V(\zeta)} d\zeta \quad (3.4)$$

$$C_D^m(\xi, t) = H\left(\sqrt[3]{\xi_{max}^3 - \xi_{min}^3} - \xi\right) f_d^m(\xi, t) \int_{\xi_{min}}^{(\xi_{max}^3 - \xi^3)^{1/3}} c(\xi, \zeta) \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, t)}{\rho_d V(\zeta)} d\zeta \quad (3.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_B^m(\xi, t) = H\left(\xi - \sqrt[3]{2\xi_{min}^3}\right) \frac{\xi^2 \rho_d V_d(\xi)}{2} \int_{\xi_{min}}^{(\xi^3 - \xi_{min}^3)^{1/3}} & \frac{c([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \zeta) f_d^m(\zeta, t)}{(\xi^3 - \zeta^3)^{2/3} \rho_d V(\zeta)} \\ & \frac{f_d^m([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, t)}{\rho_d V_d([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3})} d\zeta \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

$$c(\xi, \zeta) = \lambda(\xi, \zeta) h(\xi, \zeta) \quad (3.7)$$

Eq. (3.1) is governed by the following initial and boundary conditions:

$$f_d^m(\xi, t = 0) = f_{d,ini}^m(\xi) \quad (3.8)$$

$$f_d^m(\xi = \xi_{min}, t) v_\xi(\xi_{min}, t) = J_d^m \quad (3.9)$$

$$f_d^m(\xi = \xi_{max}, t) v_\xi(\xi_{max}, t) = 0 \quad (3.10)$$

Here f_d^m is the mass density function of the dispersed phase, t is the time dimension, ξ is the bubble diameter (inner coordinate in the property space), $\dot{m}_{d,out}$, $\dot{m}_{d,in}$ are the outlet resp. inlet mass flow rate of the dispersed phase, V_R is the reactor volume, $f_{d,in}^m$ is the inlet mass density

function of the dispersed phase, $v_\xi(\xi, t)$ is the velocity in property space in the following just growth rate, $V_d(\xi)$ volume of a bubble with size ξ , m_d mass of a bubble with size ξ , $B_B^m(\xi, t)$, $B_D^m(\xi, t)$ are sources regarding breakage birth and death events, $C_B^m(\xi, t)$, $C_D^m(\xi, t)$ are sources regarding coalescence birth and death events, $b(\xi)$ the breakage frequency, ξ_{\max}, ξ_{\min} are the maximal resp. minimal size of bubble size, ζ the integration variable resp. the mother bubble, ν the average number of new bubbles after breakage, $P(\xi, \zeta)$ the daughter size distribution function, $c(\xi, \zeta)$ the coalescence frequency, $\lambda(\xi, \zeta)$ coalescence efficiency, $h(\xi, \zeta)$ collision frequency, $f_{d,\text{ini}}^m(\xi)$ initial mass density function, and J_d^m is the mass nucleation rate.

Eq. (3.1) has additional terms compared to the PBE that usually appear in the literature [26, 33]. The second and third term on the left-hand side of Eq. (3.1) appears due to the unresolved convective fluxes over the physical space and describe the change of f_d^m due to in and outflows of the system under consideration (see Supplementary Information S.3.1 for a derivation). The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (3.1) describes the mass increase due to mass transfer from the continuous to the dispersed phase. This term results from the transformation of a number into a mass-based PBE. Derivation and a detailed discussion of this term can be found elsewhere [16]. Furthermore, in Eq. (3.3) - Eq. (3.6) Heaviside functions appear in the equations these were introduced for strict mass conservation [28].

Eq. (3.1) has a first order differential operator with respect to ξ which requires a boundary condition to be set, here Eq. (3.9) which describes nucleation processes. Note that other authors [27, 29] add this process as a point source inside of Eq. (3.1). Depending on the solution method used, these two approaches are identical but they might also differ from each other, so attention must be paid. Eq. (3.10) is called regularity condition [46], which ensures that no mass can leave the system over the property domains boundary's. In a mathematical sense it is not a boundary condition that can be enforced, however it must be inherently satisfied by the system, which is a modeling problem. This can be fulfilled, for example, by ensuring that $v_\xi(\xi_{\max})$ assumes zero, or that the domain with respect to ξ is chosen so large that f_d^m never assumes values greater than zero, presuming $f_d^m(\xi_{\max})$ was initialized with zero.

3.3. Constitutive Equations

To close the model constitutive equations are needed for $\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}$, $f_{d,\text{in}}^m(\xi)$, $\frac{dm_d}{dt}$, $\frac{d\rho_d}{dt}$, ν , $b(\xi)$, $P(\xi, \zeta)$, $\lambda(\xi, \zeta)$, $h(\xi, \zeta)$ and J_d^m . $\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}$ is determined on the basis of an integral balance about the volume of the reactor (see Eq. (S.16)). A derivation is given in the Supplementary Information S.3.1, using the assumption that the volume of the fluids enclosed is constant in time, so that the mass outflow rate is the difference between the mass inflow rate minus the mass flow rate due to phase change. As inlet distribution $f_{d,\text{in}}^m(\xi)$ the initial $f_{d,\text{ini}}^m(\xi)$ is used since it is assumed that only the inlet distribution was present at $t = 0$. For $\frac{dm_d}{dt}$ a simple two-film theory approach with constant driving force (cf. assumptions Section 3.1) is used (see Eq. (S.15)), ν is constant and has the value two, meaning only a binary breakage, J_d^m is constant and assumes a value based on the investigated case, usually zero. For $b(\xi)$ the model according to Coualoglou *et al.* [47] (see Eq. (S.7)), for $P(\xi, \zeta)$ the distribution function according to Laakkonen *et al.* [48] (see

Eq. (S.8)) and for $\lambda(\xi, \zeta), h(\xi, \zeta)$ the model according to Coulaloglou *et al.* [47] (see Eq. (S.3), Eq. (S.2)) are mainly used. The corresponding equations are summarized in the Supplementary Information S.2.

3.4. Methods of Solution

3.4.1. Overview

The four discretization methods for determining the density function directly from the PBE used in this paper, are the weighed residual spectral orthogonal collocation (OC), the fixed pivot technique (FPT), the meshless radial basis method (RBM) and our develop method, called the finite volume method with Gauss quadrature (FVMG).

The following provides an overview of the mathematical details necessary for discussing the various methods. For more comprehensive insights please refer to the source publications [27, 28, 33] and textbooks [49, 50].

To compare the four methods, they can be roughly divided into six building blocks: discretization of the accumulation/transient term, grid points (in physical and in this chapter especially in property space), convection in physical space, convection in property space, integrals and the interpolation scheme within the integrals.

The transient term is discretized for all methods using a standard ordinary differential equation (ODE) time stepper (see Supplementary Information S.5 for details). Except for OC, the grid points in property space are all equidistant in the respective examined domain (see Eq. (S.46)). OC uses Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto (GLL) nodes as grid points. Integration is performed with the exception of the FPT by using a Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule. For further differences and the convection scheme, the four methods are briefly introduced.

3.4.2. Weighed Residual Spectral Orthogonal Collocation – OC

OC uses a truncated series expansion to approximate the solution function $f \approx f_{\text{approx}} = \sum_i^{N_\xi} \omega_i \varphi_i$, where f is the exact solution function, f_{approx} an approximate solution function, N_ξ is the number of grid points resp. basis functions and ω_i the coefficients of the basis functions φ_i . Lagrangian functions are chosen as basis functions, which have special properties such as orthogonality. Due to the available approximation function, the convection in the property and physical space can be obtained by analytical derivation of it and the function value at the integration points can be obtained directly by evaluating f_{approx} , resulting in a derivative resp. interpolation scheme of higher order accuracy. The unknown coefficients of the basis functions ω_i are determined using the method of weighted residuals utilizing a weighting function, in the case of OC Dirac delta functions.

3.4.3. Meshless Radial Basis Method – RBM

The RBM approximates f similarly to OC with an truncated series expansion. Radial basis functions such as multiquadrics are used as basis functions. This radial basis functions depend on the distance between the grid points and a shape factor κ . Alzyod *et al.* [27] uses Algorithm 7.1 according to Griffiths [51] to determine it. The algorithm aims to bring the condition number of the interpolant matrix, which is used to interpolate and determine the derivative, into a given range. This requires an initial shape factor κ_0 and a step width $\delta\kappa = 1 \times 10^{-4}$. Due to the available approximation function, as with OC, the derivative can be easily determined and the function values can be determined directly at the integration points without the need for a separate interpolation scheme.

3.4.4. Fixed Pivot Technique – FPT

The FPT decomposes the PBE into classes resp. sections and chooses zero-order polynomials as the basis function, which leads to solving the PBE as a histogram. Further the integrals of the breakage and coalescence terms can be considered as a simple summation. Based on the derivation, a further an additional integral of the breakage and coalescence terms over the class width appears, which is determined using the mean value theorem for integrals. An interpolation scheme within the breakage and coalescence terms does not appear directly, rather the particles born between the centers of the classes are distributed to the neighboring classes using rules based on moment conservation. A convection scheme is not part of the standard method according to Kumar *et al.* [33]. Lehnigk *et al.* [29] uses a first order upwind finite volume scheme for the property space. However, other schemes for physical and property space should be possible.

3.4.5. Finite Volume Method With Gauss Quadrature – FVMG

Our FVMG method is characterized by the fact that it uses numerical procedures familiar to the engineer, is easy to understand and to implement and that the convection in the property and physical space is strictly mass conserving due to the FVM part. FVMG uses a Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule for the integration like OC and RBM ensuring higher order integration accuracy. For convection in physical and property space a high resolution finite volume scheme is used that is at least second order accurate in areas of smooth solution and does not oscillate around of discontinuities. As interpolation scheme to the integration nodes a piece-wise cubic Hermite spline interpolation. The equations required to implement the FVMG are summarized in the Supplementary Information S.4. For further details, please refer to the textbooks [52–54], for example.

3.5. Implementation Details and Tools

All methods were implemented in the Julia programming language in Version 1.10 [55]. A detailed list of the packages used including their version and some details of the used ODE and

steady-state solver can be found in the Supplementary Information S.5. The number of grid points N_ξ and integration nodes $N_{\xi,\text{int}}$ used differ depending on the case and are listed in the Supplementary Information S.2.3.

3.6. Analytical Solutions and Error Measure

In order to analyze the performance of the different methods, some analytical solutions of simplified PBE from the literature [36–42] are used. As error measure the Euclidean norm of the derivation between the normalized density function resulting from the simulation $\hat{f}_{\text{d,sim}}(\xi, t)$ and from a analytic solution $\hat{f}_{\text{d,ana}}(\xi, t)$ is used.

$$Error = \left\| \hat{f}_{\text{d,ana}}(\xi, t) - \hat{f}_{\text{d,sim}}(\xi, t) \right\|_2 \quad \text{for } t > 0 \quad (3.11)$$

It should be noted that the same time steps are employed for all solution methods, although the grid points in the property space may differ. Consequently, a separate analytical solution is calculated for each method. The normalized density function is obtained by division by its area (see Eq. (S.40)).

In this work four different test cases (A-D) are considered. In the first two cases, constant growth in the property space without breakage and coalescence is analyzed with: (A) constant growth with a multi-modal initial distribution [39] and (B) constant growth of a nucleation process [37]. In the third case (C) only breakage occurs [42] and in the fourth case (D) only breakage and coalescence [38]. The analytical solutions can be found in the source publications [37–39, 42]. The applied model parameters are listed in the Supplementary Information Tab. S.1.

3.7. Definition of Sensitivity and Parameter Studies

Based on a classical design strategy for STR using [56, 57] and in analogy to the experiments, a default case is defined, which is summarized in Tab. S.2. It was taken into account that in STR breakage dominates over coalescence. The gas holdup, which mainly results from the power input resp. the energy dissipation rate and gas flux, was calculated using the correlation according to Moucha *et al.* [58] for a single Rushton turbine. This default case serves as the basis for the sensitivity and parameter study, in which mainly steady-state solutions will be considered. In the study, almost all model parameters are varied in one-at-a-time analysis, which is divided into four parts:

The first study assesses the influence of kernel parameters and selection. The kernel parameters of the default case are varied to ascertain their sensitivity to changes, thereby providing insights for parameter estimation and model behaviour. In addition to the default case, a second kernel set comprising of Laakkonen *et al.* [48] for the breakage frequency, Prince *et al.* [59] for the collision frequency, R.B. Diemer [60] for the daughter size distribution function and Chester [61] for the coalescence efficiency is investigated. The second kernel set parameters were manually adjusted so that these conserved mass, satisfy the regularity condition and generate a similar

integral amount of breakage (0.03 kg s^{-1}) and coalescence (0.01 kg s^{-1}) as the default case based on the inlet BSD.

In the second study, an existing reactor concept is optimized by varying the process conditions (gas holdup, gas flux, power input). The gas holdup in a STR is mainly influenced by two effects: first the rising velocity of the bubbles and second the recirculation of the gas phase. The first effect is determined by the size and shape as well as the property data of the fluids. The second effect depends on the flow field. The flow field depends on numerous parameters such as the type and dimensions of the stirrer, baffles, stirrer speed, property data of the fluids, etc. Since we keep the gas holdup constant over time and assume that all bubbles have the same residence time, we cannot model the influence of the first effect. The second effect is investigated in an artificial study in which the gas holdup is varied at constant power input and gas flux. In the experiment, this study could not be carried out at least in the wide range, because as described the gas holdup depends on many parameters. However, the general behavior of the model should be investigated. When examining the gas flux and the power input, a distinction is made between two cases: in one case, the gas holdup is kept constant, as in all other studies, and in the other case, the influence of the gas flux or the power input is considered using the correlation presented by Moucha *et al.* [58] that describes the gas holdup ($\alpha_d = 0.01686 (\varepsilon \rho_c)^{0.6241} j_d^{0.5669}$). Note, it was ensured that the STR would not start to flood [57, 62].

In the third study, the influence of the gas sparger (mean, width and mode of the inlet resp. initial BSD) is investigated since the sparger is an essential component of any multiphase STR and its influence on the behavior of the dispersed phase is difficult to study with models that do not include the PBE.

In the fourth and final study, the influence of the physiochemical properties (surface tension, viscosity liquid phase, mass density gas and liquid phase, mass transfer) is examined.

The third and fourth studies are provided in the Supplementary Information S.1. The four studies are discussed based on the following (output) variables: the mass density function f_d^m , the Sauter mean diameter (SMD) ξ_{32} , and the interfacial area density a . The SMD and the interfacial area density are determined from the second and third moment of the predicted mass density function, see Eq. (S.20) and Eq. (S.19), respectively. All results of the studies are compared with findings from the literature, if available. The parameters applied in the studies are summarized in Supplementary Information S.2.

3.8. Preliminary Application to Measured BSD and Parameter Estimation

In order to apply the model to the experimentally investigated STR (cf. Section 2), the parameters in Tab. S.4 are utilized. Furthermore, the measured initial BSD and the inlet BSD, which is assumed to be the measured initial BSD, must be specified. As the kernels and their parameters are not yet predictive and are case-dependent, a known issue in the community [48, 63–65], they must be adapted to experiments. This was accomplished by minimizing the sum of the symmetric χ^2 -distance between the experimental and simulated normalized number density function over

all time steps. Prior to the optimization, all kernel parameters are normalized to a scale of unity since they span over many orders of magnitude. In order to obtain only physical solutions (e.g. no artificial mass loss), a regularization was added, which acts as a penalty for high mass loss. Furthermore, a grid search was used to select suitable starting parameters and lower and upper parameter bounds so that the local minimum found by optimization coincides with the global minimum.

Details of the packages and solvers used are given in the Supplementary Information S.5.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Comparison of the Numerical Solution Methods

Fig. 4.1 depicts a dimensionless and scaled number density function f^s as a function of a dimensionless and scaled diameter ξ^s for the four test A-D cases described in Section 3.4. The nondimensionalization and scaling of the axes were implemented to facilitate a straightforward comparison of the four cases.

Figure 4.1.: Dimensionless and scaled number density function f^s as function of a dimensionless and scaled diameter ξ^s . Comparison of the numerical solutions (symbols) obtained from the four different solvers with the respective analytical solutions (lines) for the four test cases A-D. The color represents different points in time.

Fig. 4.1A shows the case according to Qamar *et al.* [39] of pure growth of a multi-modal distribution function. It can be seen that the OC, RBM and FVMG methods can reproduce the time evolution well: $Error = (0.015, 0.041, 0.340)$. The high accuracy of OC and RBM results from the available analytic derivative with higher order accuracy. But it should be noted if

the algorithm of Griffiths [51] to determine the shape factor is initialized with $\kappa_0 = 0.01$ instead of $\kappa_0 = 10$, we obtain a shape factor of $\kappa = 0.064$ instead of $\kappa = 0.076$ which leads to an $Error = 2 \times 10^{52}$, which is far away from the solution and even smaller changes, e.g. an $\kappa = 0.071$, already produce nonphysical negative values ($Error = 1.806$). This means that the algorithm [51] does not provide unique solutions and that the accuracy depends strongly and very sensitively on the shape factor. The FVMG tends to underestimate the peaks despite the high resolution scheme, but this is just second order accurate and could be replaced by a higher order scheme. FPT shows a strong numerical diffusion due to the first order upwind scheme ($Error = 2.349$).

Fig. 4.1B shows the case according to Hounslow *et al.* [37] of constant growth with simultaneous nucleation. FVMG and FPT can track the fronts, whereas FPT is more prone to numerical diffusion due to the lower order scheme, $Error = (14.31, 21.31)$. OC shows strong oscillations especially at ξ_{\min} caused by the step gradient introduced by the nucleation process resp. the boundary condition, $Error = 18.61$. The oscillations originate from the higher order approximation function. RBM also produces oscillations, but more in the area of the front also caused by the higher order scheme $Error = 8.25$. Note that RBM and OC have a comparatively small error but the fronts are insufficiently tracked and they oscillate. The oscillation in particular amplifies with increasing time. Furthermore the OC and RBM provide strong solutions where the boundary conditions are rigorously enforced, ensuring their precise fulfillment. In conjunction with the PBE, which encompasses integrals that span the entire property space, particles that die due to coalescence or are born due to breakage are irretrievably lost. To prevent this mass loss, an integral boundary condition can be set. Alternatively, it can be imposed that the smallest particles can neither be born by breakage nor die by coalescence, e.g. by constraints or by appropriate choice and parameterization of the kernel functions. While the FVMG and FPT provide weak solutions, this is not a problem and nucleation is simply considered as an additional flux over the lower boundary of the property domain without any complicated time-dependent integral boundary condition or artificial constraints.

For the third case according to Ziff *et al.* [42], where only breakage and no coalescence and growth are considered, the methods RBM, FVMG and OC provide an accurate solution, $Error = (0.24, 0.23, 0.21)$ of the density functions, see Fig. 4.1C. The finding that all methods performed similarly well can be attributed to the fact that they all used the same quadrature rule for the breakage birth term. The differences result only from the interpolation scheme and the grid points. FPT, on the other hand, overestimates the trend caused by the zero-order approximation of the integration, $Error = 20.38$. The $Error$ can only be reduced to 10.08 when 300 grid points are used.

In the last case according to J. McCoy *et al.* [38], where simultaneous breakage and coalescence but no growth is considered (see Fig. 4.1C). The analytic solution was transformed to a mass-length based form and the domain was chosen to be $\xi = [2, 1000] \times 10^{-6}$ m to be closer to the experimentally investigated system of this work (cf. Section 2). The methods FPT, FVMG and OC provide an accurate numerical solution of the density function. The error of the OC method is lowest, and highest for the FPT method, $Error = (0.7, 3.8, 4.9) \times 10^{-3}$. However, it should be noted that the number of grid points in OC had to be reduced to 80 in order to obtain a stable

solution. Since OC uses GLL grid points, which are very dense close to the domain boundaries, numerical problems arise when integrating and interpolating the denominator in the coalescence birth term. The hole denominator within in the coalescence birth term assumes very large values at the respective integration limits, which is difficult to integrate accurately and to interpolate stable with a higher order interpolation scheme. This problem is exacerbated by the use of property domains on smaller scales and denser grid points. While nondimensionalization and scaling of the dependent and independent variables can mitigate this issue, it is not a complete solution. This is because the GLL points will remain closely spaced as the number of grid points increases, as is the case with breakage-dominated problems. Restricting the range permitted for breakage and coalescence only addresses this issue in certain instances. Another approach is to express the PBE in number length or number volume based form, which significantly simplifies the mathematical form of the breakage and coalescence terms. However, this approach also introduces new challenges. For instance, volume as a property leads to very small numbers, which can result in poorly prescribed grids and large numbers that must be balanced for a number-based PBE, increasing the susceptibility to round-off errors. Further research is needed to address these issues.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that only 80 points were necessary for the OC in contrast to 200 points for the other methods in order to achieve a high accuracy. No optimal shape factor could be found for the RBM, so no solution could be obtained. Important in contrast to Alzyod *et al.* [27] the PBE was solved mass length based in the domain $\xi = [2, 1000] \times 10^{-6}$ m instead of number length based in the scaled domain $\xi = [2, 5] \mu\text{m}$. We assume that the algorithm [51] has problems with the domain on the small scales.

In conclusion, it can be stated that none of the examined methods demonstrated a clear superiority over the others. The FPT results in numerical diffusion, which may be improved by employing a different convection scheme. Due to the zero-order integration, an accurate calculation of the breakage and coalescence terms may necessitate the use of numerous classes, which are numerically demanding. RBM provides exact results for complex convection-dominated problems. However, there are issues with nucleation and small-scale property spaces. These issues are primarily attributed to the shape factor and its calculation. Mesh-free methods, in general, are promising methods to provide a robust solution of the PBE, as evidenced by the work of Garg *et al.* [66]. However, further work is needed to fully realize their potential. OC is by far the most accurate method, even for low grid point counts. Once the aforementioned issues are resolved, the highly accurate method can also become a robust numerical method. This is not the case, and further development of the method is not our primary objective; we leave this to other authors. Our proposed method, FVMG, has been demonstrated to be sufficiently accurate, robust, and easy to understand and implement. Consequently, an engineer can expeditiously adapt this method and, if necessary, specialize it to her / his problem with the assistance of well-known methods from the FVM environment, such as non-uniform grids, different convection and diffusion schemes, and specialized solvers, among others. Therefore, only our FVMG method is considered in the following parameter study.

4.2. Sensitivity and Parameter Analysis

4.2.1. Study on Breakage and Coalescence Kernels and Parameters

Fig. 4.2A and B illustrate the SMD ξ_{32} , and interfacial area density a , respectively, as functions of the linear scaling factor of breakage frequency C_{bf} and coalescence frequency C_{cf} (cf. Eq. (S.7)-(S.2)). Similarly, Fig. 4.2C and D present the mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for various linear scaling factor of breakage and coalescence frequency.

Figure 4.2.: (A-B): Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of linear scaling factor of breakage frequency C_{bf} (A) and coalescence frequency C_{cf} (B). (C-D): Mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for the different breakage frequency C_{bf} (C) and coalescence frequency C_{cf} (D). Applied parameters see Tab. S.2 and Tab. S.3.

As expected, the breakage frequency has a strong influence on the model predictions (see Fig. 4.2A and D). The SMD drops rapidly and converges slowly to a constant value from approx. $C_{bf} \approx 0.2$. The fact that the bubbles cannot become smaller is due to the breakage kernel used, which is parameterized in such a way that no breakage below a certain bubble size is possible (cf. Fig. 4.2C). It is known that a lower limit exists [67], but it depends strongly on the material system, power input and stirrer, for example. The re-increase at $\xi = 0.2$ mm in Fig. 4.2C after the maximum originates from the inlet distribution. Due to the constant gas holdup, the interfacial area density behaves inversely according to $a \propto \alpha_d / \xi_{32}$.

In consideration of the variation in coalescence frequency (see Fig. 4.2B and D), the inverse effect of breakage is observed: bubbles increase in size and the interfacial area density decreases

with rising coalescence. A comparable degree of sensitivity to that observed with breakage does not manifest, although a similar flattening of the slope can be discerned at higher coalescence frequencies.

This study helps to identify the range in which the BSD are sensitive to the breakage and coalescence parameters. This knowledge is important for selecting reasonable initial values or parameter ranges for parameter estimation when calibrating the model to measured data. This study was also carried out for the two other breakage and coalescence parameters that influence the bubble size dependence. The results are not shown here.

Fig. 4.3 shows the analysis of the influence of the kernel selection, where the SMD ξ_{32} is depicted as a function of time t and the mass density function f_d^m as function of the bubble diameter ξ for different time steps for the two investigated kernel sets (used kernels see Supplementary Information S.2.1).

Figure 4.3.: (A): Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of time t for two different kernel sets (line style, used kernels see Supplementary Information S.2.1). (B): Mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for two different kernel sets.

It can be clearly seen that the two kernel sets differ just slightly from each other. The second kernel set predict a slightly higher steady-state SMD. A similar observation that different sets of kernels hardly differ from each other after a parameter adjustment has already been made in a previous publication of us [12]. Furthermore, if available, other kernel functions of the above-mentioned authors [47, 48, 59–61] and those of [68, 69] were varied, showing a similar behavior (not shown in this work). This behavior is due to the fact that the process is affected by the inlet distribution, that the kernels are very flexible, have a similar theoretical background and thus have similar model equations. However, this should not lead to a generally applicable statement that the choice of kernel is irrelevant. Other kernels such as multifractal [70], cascade kernel [71] or other kernels such as those summarized in [72, 73] could lead to different results.

4.2.2. Variation of Process Conditions

Fig. 4.4A-C depict the SMD ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of different process conditions: gas holdup α_d , gas flux j_d , power input or energy dissipation rate ε . Fig. 4.4D-F

shows the mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for the different process conditions. In the study of the gas flux and power input, as described in Section 3.7, two cases are distinguished: constant gas holdup (dashed line) and gas holdup according to the correlation of Moucha *et al.* [58] (solid line), whereby the non-varying parameter is kept constant, e.g. in the gas flux study, the power input is always constant. The BSDs for the constant gas holdup case could be found in the Supplementary Information Fig. S.5.

Figure 4.4.: (A-C): Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of different process conditions, with varying gas holdup according to Moucha *et al.* [58] (solid line) and constant gas hold-up (dashed line) in B,C. (D-F): Mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for different process conditions. Process conditions: (A,D) - gas holdup α_d ; (B,E) - gas flux j_d ; (D,F) energy dissipation rate ε .

Fig. 4.4A and D demonstrate the influence of gas holdup at constant power input and gas flux on the SMD and the mass density function, respectively. The SMD initially exhibits a decrease and then an increase with rising gas holdup. The anticipated increase is consistent with the experimental findings reported by Alves *et al.* [74]. In the model, the coalescence rate (cf. Eq. (S.2) and Eq. (S.3)) increases with gas holdup as documented by Tsouris *et al.* [75]. The increase in the coalescence rate is responsible for the increase in the SMD. However, at very low values of gas holdup ($\alpha_d \leq 7\%$) the breakage rate obviously dominates over the coalescence, so that the SMD initially decreases.

As the gas flux is increased (see Fig. 4.4B and E), the SMD also increases in accordance with the literature [76, 77]. This trend is observed irrespective of whether the gas holdup is regarded as constant or varying. In the case of constant gas holdup, the residence time of the bubbles in the reactor decreases directly with increasing gas flux. Given the short residence time, the

impact of breakage and coalescence events within the reactor on the BSD is reduced, while the SMD is predominantly influenced by the inlet BSD with an SMD of $\approx 198 \mu\text{m}$. In the case of varying gas holdup, the fundamental behavior is analogous to that observed with a constant holdup. However, the predicted SMDs are higher with increasing gas flux than with a constant gas holdup. As the gas flux rises, the gas holdup increases, leading to an elevated incidence of coalescence events. In the case of a variable gas holdup, the interfacial area density increases. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that the gas holdup increases at a rate that is greater than that of the SMD. At constant gas holdup, the interfacial area density is inversely proportional to the SMD. Note that, depending on the parameterization of the kernel, the opposite behavior of decreasing SMD and increasing interfacial area density at constant gas holdup can also occur, once again emphasizing the importance of parameterizing the kernel correctly.

In the context of energy dissipation rate or power input, respectively (see Fig. 4.4C and F), it is evident that regardless of the gas holdup case, increasing the dissipation rate from $0.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$ to about $2.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$ leads to a reduction in bubble size. This behavior is consistent with the well-documented phenomenon that the breakage rate increases with energy dissipation rate, as observed in previous studies [74, 78, 79]. In the case of varying gas holdup, the SMD decreases less strongly than in the case of constant gas holdup. Indeed, for large power inputs, the SMD even increases once more ($\varepsilon > 2.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$). This is due to the fact that, with an increase in gas holdup, coalescence also rises, as evidenced by Polli *et al.* [80] and Oolman *et al.* [81]. Consequently, this phenomenon effectively masks the impact of the power input. The behavior of the interfacial area density can be explained in a manner analogous to that employed in the analysis of the gas flux study.

In conclusion, the model demonstrates a correlation between the observed trends of increased gas holdup and gas flux, which result in larger bubbles, and the increased power input, which leads to smaller bubbles. Nevertheless, it is essential to address the limitation of the model, which is unable to predict the gas holdup. One potential approach to address this issue is the deployment of a size-dependent residence time model for the gas phase. This model should account for two key effects: the rising velocity of bubbles and the flow field, particularly the backmixing of the gas phase (cf. Section 3.7).

It is a prerequisite for future calibration of the model in a manner analogous to that employed in our previous work on the BCs [13]. In that instance, we were able to calibrate the model for at single axial position for two gas fluxes and to predict both the BSD and the gas volume fraction for other gas fluxes outside the calibrated range.

The third and fourth study (cf. Section 3.7) on the influence of the sparger design and the physiochemical properties (surface tension, viscosity liquid phase, mass density gas and liquid phase, mass transfer) on the BSD are documented in the Supplementary Information S.1. These studies demonstrate that despite the limitations of the model, a considerable number of predicted trends are consistent with observations reported in the literature. Furthermore, these simulation studies also confirm that our FVMG method is both robust and efficient for solving these systems of equations.

4.3. Model Demonstration: Application to Experimental Data

Fig. 4.5 illustrates the comparison between the experimentally measured BSD and the BSD predicted by the model at varying time points. The initial BSD value was utilized as both the initial and inlet condition. The four model parameters employed to fit the breakage and coalescence kernels were estimated using the BSDs derived from a time series measurement.

The results demonstrate that the model is capable of reproducing the BSD in principle. However, due to the model's inability to describe the gas holdup in the STR, it is not yet feasible to utilize this model for predicting the impact of process parameter variations on the behavior of the dispersed gas phase, as is possible with our bubble column model. Nevertheless, this result represents a significant initial step in the model development process.

Figure 4.5.: Normalized number density function \hat{f}_d^n as a function of the bubble diameter ξ for different time steps t . Definitions: lines - simulations, symbols - experiments, star marker - inlet/initial value. Applied parameters see Tab. S.4. Experimental data see Supplementary Material.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In this study, the multifluid population balance model (MPB) was employed to analyze a non-reactive two-phase stirred tank reactor (STR). The objective of this study was to identify a robust and efficient method for solving the resulting integro-partial differential equations. Four distinct solution methodologies were subjected to evaluation, with one, namely the finite volume method with Gauss quadrature (FVMG), being developed within the context of this investigation. The efficacy of the methods was evaluated through their application to problems for which analytical solutions are available. The results demonstrate that no single method emerges as a clear outperformer in comparison to the others. All methods have both advantages and disadvantages. The proposed method, FVMG, has been demonstrated to be sufficiently accurate, robust, and readily comprehensible and implementable. Consequently, this constitutes a valuable contribution to the field and has the potential to facilitate the application of the MPB for describing dispersed multiphase reactors.

The FVMG was utilized for parameter and sensitivity studies with the MPB of the STR. Four different studies were carried out. The first study investigated the influence of the breakage and coalescence kernels on the bubble size distribution (BSD). The simulation results show the expected trends. This study also provides information on the parameter ranges in which the calculated BSD is sensitive to the model parameters. This information is important for selecting reasonable initial values for parameter estimation when calibrating the model to measured data. The second study examined the influence of the variation of different process conditions on the BSD. The limitation of the model, namely its inability to describe the gas holdup in the STR, was addressed by considering two cases: one with a constant gas holdup and the other with a varying gas holdup according to an empirical correlation. The general trends are in accordance with the findings of experimental studies. The studies three and four presented in the Supplementary Information S.1 concerning the physicochemical properties and the design of the gas sparger largely confirm the trends described in the literature, although some limitations are apparent. It was also observed that the parameterization of kernel models has a significant impact on the predicted trends. Overall, the FVMG was demonstrated to be a robust and efficient method through the parameter and sensitivity analysis, exhibiting no numerical instabilities and rapid convergence of the solver.

Ultimately, the model parameters were calibrated to the experimental data obtained from the BSD in the STR. The simulation and experimental results were observed to be in close agreement with one another. In order to obtain a reliable prediction, it was necessary to utilize all BSDs of a given time series from an experiment in the preliminary parameter determination. Nevertheless, the model is not yet suitable for predicting large ranges of process parameters, as is possible with our MPB of the bubble column (BC). In contrast to the MPB for STRs, the MPB for BCs can

describe the gas holdup.

In conclusion, the MPB of the STR, in conjunction with our novel solution methodology, FVMG, proved to be a valuable tool for investigating the intricate behavior of the dispersed gas phase within the STR. However, the model also exhibited limitations. The inability of the model to describe the gas holdup limits the applicability of the MBP for scale-up and design of real reactors, as the influence of variation of parameters (design, process conditions, property data) on the properties of the gas phase (and on heat and mass transfer) cannot be adequately predicted. The primary objective of future work will be to identify modelling approaches that enable the description of this important property. Furthermore, the application to systems with reaction and/or heat and mass transfer will be carried out to further evaluate the performance of the model approach. This work represents a significant advancement in our efforts to develop a model that can describe the complex behavior of a dispersed multiphase system within a STR and that requires only a minimal number of empirical equations and parameters.

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Nomenclature

Latin Letters

a	Interfacial area density	m^{-1}
A	Cross section of the reactor	m^2
$d\mathbf{A}$	Vectorial surface element	m^2
d_R	Reactor diameter	m
$B_D^m(\xi, z)$	Death rate due to bubble breakage	$\text{kg m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$B_B^m(\xi, z)$	Birth rate due to bubble breakage	$\text{kg m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$b(\xi)$	Breakage frequency	s^{-1}
$C_B^m(\xi, z)$	Birth rate due to bubble coalescence	$\text{kg m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$C_D^m(\xi, z)$	Death rate due to bubble coalescence	$\text{kg m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$c(\zeta, \xi)$	Coalescence frequency	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
C_i	Adjustable parameter of the breakage and coalescence kernel	
C_{bf}	Linear scaling factor of the breakage frequency	-
C_{cf}	Linear scaling factor of the coalescence frequency	-
<i>Error</i>	Error measure according to Eq. (3.11)	%
f	Exact solution function	
f_{approx}	Approximate solution function	
f_d^m	Mass-based density function; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	kg m^{-4}
F_i	Flux at phase i	
g_i	Slope at grid point i	
$h(\zeta, \xi)$	Collision frequency	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
$H(\xi)$	Heaviside function of variable ξ	-
j_d	Gas flux	m s^{-1}
J_d^m	Mass nucleation rate	$\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
k_{MT}	Mass transfer coefficient	m s^{-1}
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	kg s^{-1}
m_d	Mass of a bubble with size ξ	kg
m_d	Mass of the dispersed phase	kg
n_d	Number density	m^{-3}
N_ξ	Number of grid points	-
$N_{\xi, \text{int}}$	Number of integration points	-
$P(\zeta, \xi)$	Daughter size distribution function	-
p	Pressure	Pa
\mathbf{r}	Physical space domain $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)^T$	m

continued ...

... continued

s_i	Smoothness indicator at phase i	-
t	Time dimension	s
v_ξ	Growth rate	m s^{-1}
\mathbf{v}_r	Velocity in physical space	m s^{-1}
$V_d(\xi)$	Volume of a bubble of diameter ξ	m^3
V_R	Reactor volume	m^3
V_k	Volume of the k -phase	m^3
\bar{V}_ξ	Average volume of the bubbles	m^3
w	Mass fraction	kg kg^{-1}
Δw	Mass transfer driving force	kg kg^{-1}

Greek Letters

α_d	Volume fraction of the gas phase	-
Γ_d	Mass transfer rate per volume due to phase change	$\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-3}$
$\delta\kappa_0$	Step width of the algorithm proposed by [51]	-
δV_R	Surface of the reactor volume V_R	m^2
$\Delta\xi$	Cell width of the ξ -grid	m
ε	Turbulent energy dissipation rate	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
ζ	Integration variable, parent bubble	m
κ	Shape factor a the basis function of the RBM	-
κ_0	Initial shape factor of the algorithm proposed by [51]	-
$\lambda(\zeta)$	Coalescence efficiency	-
μ_k	Viscosity of the k -phase	Pa s
μ_0	Mean value of the inlet distribution	m
μ_1	Value of the second peak of a bi-modal inlet distribution	m
ν	Average number of bubbles after breakage	-
ξ	Property space coordinate representing the diameter of spherical bubbles, child bubble; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	m
ξ_{32}	Sauter mean diameter	m
$\tilde{\xi}_i$	Integration nodes in the reference domain	-
$\tilde{\xi}_i^*$	Integration nodes in the property domain	m
ρ_k	Mass density of the k -phase	kg m^{-3}
σ	Surface tension between of the continuous and dispersed phase	J m^{-2}
σ_0	Standard deviation of the inlet distribution	m
φ_i	Basis function $\Phi(s_i)$	Flux lim- iter
ψ	Basis functions of a truncated series expansion	-
ω_i	Basis function coefficients	

continued ...

... continued

$\tilde{\omega}_i$	Quadrature weights in the reference domain	-
$\tilde{\omega}_i^*$	Quadrature weights in the property domain	-

Subscripts

0	Quantity related to the inlet distribution
ana	Analytic solution
B	Birth/ source term
c	Continuous liquid phase
d	Dispersed gas phase
D	Death/ sink term
exp	Quantity resulting from a experiment
i	Index of the basis function; index of grid point; index of adjustable parameter
in	Quantity at the inlet
ini	Initial value
k	Phase indicator index
max	Upper bound
min	Lower bound
mod	Mode of the inlet/initial distribution
out	Quantity at the outlet
sim	Quantity resulting from a simulation

Superscripts

$\hat{}$	Normalized quantity
$\bar{}$	Averaged quantity
m	Mass-based quantity
n	Number based quantity
s	Dimensionless and scaled quantity

Abbreviations

0D	Zero-dimensional in physical space
1D	One-dimensional in physical space
BC	Bubble column
BSD	Bubble size distribution
EtOH	Ethanol
FPT	Fixed pivot technique
FVMG	Finite volume method with Gauss quadrature
GLL	Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto

continued ...

... continued

KTAWSR	Kinetic theory with size resolution
MPB	Multifluid population balance model
MUSCL	Monotonic upstream-centered scheme for conservation laws
OC	Weighted residual spectral orthogonal collocation
ODE	Ordinary differential equation
OMOP	Optical multimode online probe
PBE	Population balance equation
RBM	Meshless radial basis method
RPM	Revolutions per minute
SMD	Sauter mean diameter
STR	Stirred tank reactor

S. Supplementary Information

S.1. Additional Study's

S.1.1. Variation of Physiochemical Properties

Fig. S.3 illustrate the SMD ξ_{32} and interfacial area density a , respectively, as functions of different property data. The figure of the mass density function was omitted and can be found in Supplementary Information Fig. S.4.

Figure S.1.: Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of different property data: (A) - viscosity of the continuous phase μ_c , (B) - surface tension σ , (C) - mass density of the continuous phase ρ_c , (D) - mass density of the dispersed phase ρ_d .

Despite the large viscosity range investigated, virtually no dependence of the SMD or interfacial area density could be found in the simulation (see Fig. S.1A). Experimentally, however, a strong influence towards larger bubbles is known [82, 83]. It should be noted once more that, in a real STR, the alteration of liquid phase viscosity frequently results in changes to the gas holdup. The literature presents findings indicating both a proportional and an anti-proportional relationship between gas holdup and viscosity

[84–86]. The results presented illustrate the relevance of adequate modeling of the influence of parameter variations on all variables (BSD, gas holdup) in order to ensure a valid description of the conditions in the real STR.

With respect to the surface tension (see Fig. S.1B), the fact that the diameter increases and thus the interfacial density decreases is in agreement with the experimental trend [74, 82, 87].

The slight trend of increasing breakage at increased liquid mass density shown here is also indicated by experimental observations described in literature, even if no experimental study with the liquid density as single varied parameter could be found [88, 89]. A numerical analysis of single bubble formation at an orifice according to Zahedi *et al.* [90] also confirms this trend of higher liquid density causing smaller bubbles [90]. Most likely, the movement of turbulent eddies is more efficient in highly dense liquids causing bubble breakage [90]. Although the trend observed here is less pronounced, which is due to the parameterization of the kernel.

The behavior of the SMD with regard to mass density of the gas phase is somewhat different. The SMD first increases until approx. 0.7 kg m^{-3} and then it decreases. The fact that more breakage occurs for gas densities $< 1.0 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ is due to the fact that the gas density appears in the denominator in the breakage kernel used. Experimental values with such a high resolution to be able to reproduce this trend could not be found. However, the general trend that the bubbles become smaller with increasing gas density is in line with the experimental findings [91–93].

Figures S.3A and B illustrate the SMD ξ_{32} and interfacial area density a , respectively, as functions of the mass transfer coefficient k_{MT} for a condensation and evaporation of the gas phase.

Figure S.2.: Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of the mass transfer coefficient k_{MT} for a (A) condensation and (B) evaporation of the gas phase.

If the scale of the y-axis is considered, it can be seen in both cases that the influence of the mass transfer is only very small, but corresponds to the expected behaviour that the bubbles become smaller in the case of condensation (cf. Fig. S.2A) and larger in the case of evaporation (cf. Fig. S.2B). The distributions are not shown because they hardly change noticeably.

Except for viscosity, the model, in particular the breakage and coalescence kernel of Coualoglou *et al.* [47] used, can reproduce the general trends with respect to the variation of the physiochemical properties. It should be noted, however, that the trends shown are less pronounced than those found experimentally, especially for the liquid density. Apart from the influence of the artificial assumption of constant gas holdup, we attribute this on one hand to our parameterization of the kernel and on the other hand to the fact that the kernels do not yet represent all phenomena correctly enough. Further intensive research is needed to develop generalized kernels and possibly standardized parameter estimation methods.

S.1.2. Design of the Gas Sparger

Fig. S.3A-C illustrate the SMD ξ_{32} and interfacial area density a , respectively, as functions of inlet distribution parameters: mean diameter μ_0 , standard deviation σ_0 and mean diameter of the second peak μ_1 of a bi-modal inlet distribution (see Eq. (S.13) with $mod = 2$) expressed as ratio $\frac{\mu_1}{\mu_0}$. Similarly, Fig. 4.4D-F present the mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for the various inlet distribution parameters.

Note that in this study, too, the gas holdup was kept constant, so the physical effect of larger bubbles created by larger sparger orifices having less residence time and thus less overall gas holdup cannot be reflected. However, it is acceptable for a robustness and sensitivity study.

Figure S.3.: (A-C): Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and the interfacial area density a as a function of the inlet distribution parameters. (D-F): Mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for the inlet distribution parameters. Inlet distribution parameters: (A,D) - mean diameter μ_0 ; (B,E) - σ_0 standard deviation; (C,F) - mean diameter of the second peak μ_1 of a bi-modal inlet distribution (see Eq. (S.13) with $mod = 2$) expressed as ratio $\frac{\mu_1}{\mu_0}$. Applied parameters see Tab. S.2 and Tab. S.3.

Fig. S.3A and D demonstrate the significant influence of the mean value of the inlet distribution on the SMD and the shape of the BSD. A notable decrease in interfacial area density alongside a considerable increase in bubble diameter is observed with increasing mean value of the inlet distribution. This model prediction is consistent with experimental findings reported in the literature for stirred tank reactors [94] or with respect to bubble columns [95, 96].

In contrast to the mean value, the width of the inlet distribution has a minimal impact on the SMD and interfacial area density (Fig. S.3B), indicating that breakage and coalescence occur in appear equally strong. Peaks at approx. $\xi = 0.16$ mm and hardly to see at approx. $\xi = 0.25$ mm in some distributions result from a cascading effect of binary breakage and coalescence (cf. Fig. S.3E). The occurrence of narrow distributions is associated with an elevated probability of breakage or coalescence at the peak, which in

turn gives rise to the formation of new peaks at smaller or larger bubbles. These new peaks are also prone to breakage or coalescence, thereby perpetuating the cascade. However, distributions that are wider and more continuous mitigate this effect. In any case, the numerical simulation method FVMG is capable of accurately capturing these sharp peaks without any smearing or oscillation.

In the process of designing spargers, it is typical to utilize a variety of orifice diameters to account for pressure loss within the sparger (such as within the arms of a spider sparger) and to ensure an even distribution of gas flux through all orifices. This design could result (in average) in bi-modal or multi-modal inlet distributions. Fig. S.3C and F show the influence of a bi-modal inlet distribution. It can be observed that the SMD increases as the diameter of the second peak increases and the interfacial area density decreases accordingly. An examination of Fig. S.3F reveals that while the two peaks of the inlet distribution persist, a broad transition is established, which becomes increasingly diminished as the distance between the peaks increases.

In summary, the mean value and the mode of distribution have a large influence on the BSD. However, the effect on the gas holdup, which can strongly influence the observed trends (see Section 4.2.2), cannot be neglected. Thus, these two values are likely to have a significant influence on the gas-liquid mass transfer in the reactor and thus, as expected, on the overall reactor performance. On the other hand, the width of the inlet BSD generated by the sparger seems to have little influence on the BSD. Although the estimation of the initial and inlet distribution from the sparger geometry is difficult [13], the MPB tool now offers a simple and quick way to clarify the question of how different spargers could affect the process in principle.

S.2. Model Details

S.2.1. Constitutive Equations

To close the model, the following constitutive equations were applied.

Volume of a sphere:

$$V_d(\xi) = \frac{\pi}{6} \xi^3 \quad (\text{S.1})$$

Coalescence kernel set 1 [47]:

$$h(\xi, \zeta) = C_{cf} \frac{\varepsilon^{1/3}}{1 + \alpha_d(z)} (\xi + \zeta)^2 \sqrt{\xi^{2/3} + \zeta^{2/3}} \quad (\text{S.2})$$

$$\lambda(\xi, \zeta) = \exp\left(-C_1 \frac{\mu_c \rho_c \varepsilon}{\sigma(1 + \alpha_d)^3} \left(\frac{\xi \zeta}{\xi + \zeta}\right)^4\right) \quad (\text{S.3})$$

Coalescence kernel set 2 [59, 61]:

$$h(\xi, \zeta) = \exp\left(-700 \left(\frac{\rho_c \varepsilon^{2/3} \xi_{eq}^{5/3}}{4\sigma}\right)^{1/2}\right) \quad (\text{S.4})$$

$$\lambda(\xi, \zeta) = 0.07 \exp\left(-\frac{\rho_c^{1/2} \xi_{eq}^{5/6} \varepsilon^{1/3}}{4\sigma^{1/2}} \ln\left(\frac{10^{-4}}{10^{-8}}\right)\right) \quad (\text{S.5})$$

$$\xi_{eq} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{\xi} + \frac{1}{\zeta}\right)^{-1} \quad (\text{S.6})$$

Breakage kernel set 1 [47, 48]:

$$b(\xi) = C_{bf} \frac{\varepsilon^{1/3}}{\xi^{2/3}} \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma C_2}{\rho_d \varepsilon^{2/3} \xi^{5/3}}\right) \quad (\text{S.7})$$

$$P(\xi, \zeta) = \frac{2.4 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \xi^2\right)}{V_d(\zeta)} \exp\left(-4.5 \frac{(2V(\xi) - V(\zeta))^2}{V(\zeta)^2}\right) \quad (\text{S.8})$$

$$\nu = 2.0 \quad (\text{S.9})$$

Breakage kernel set 2 [48, 60]:

$$b(\xi) = 0.3784 \varepsilon^{1/3} \operatorname{erf}\left(\sqrt{10^{-6} \frac{\sigma}{\rho_c \varepsilon^{5/3}} + 10^{-5} \frac{\mu_d}{\rho_d \rho_c \varepsilon^{1/3} \xi^{4/3}}}\right) \quad (\text{S.10})$$

$$P(\xi, \zeta) = \left(\frac{\Gamma(q\nu)}{\Gamma(q)\Gamma(q(\nu-1))}\right) \left(\frac{\xi}{\zeta}\right)^{3(q-1)} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\xi}{\zeta}\right)^3\right)^{q(\nu-1)-1} \frac{\xi^2}{\zeta^3} \quad (\text{S.11})$$

$$\nu = 2.0, q = 2.0 \quad (\text{S.12})$$

Initial/Inlet Distribution:

$$f_{d,ini}^m(\xi) = \frac{\rho_d \alpha_{d,ini}}{mod} \sum_{i=0}^{mod-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_i^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\xi - \mu_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2}\right) \quad (\text{S.13})$$

$$f_{d,in}^m(\xi) = f_{d,ini}^m(\xi) \quad (\text{S.14})$$

Mass transfer:

$$\frac{dm_d}{dt} = \pi \xi^2 \rho_d(t) k_{MT} \Delta w \quad (\text{S.15})$$

Outlet mass flow rate:

$$\dot{m}_{out} = \dot{m}_{in} + V_R \left(\int_{\xi_{min}}^{\xi_{max}} \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{V_d(\xi)} \frac{1}{\rho_d} \frac{dm_d}{dt} d\xi + J_d^m \right) - \alpha_d V_R \frac{\partial \rho_d(t)}{\partial t} \quad (\text{S.16})$$

The new symbols introduced in the above equations are specified in the Nomenclature. A derivation of Eq. (S.16) can be found in the Supplementary Information S.3.1.

S.2.2. Additional Equations

The additional equations used are listed below.

Number-based to mass-based density function:

$$f_d^n(\xi, t) = \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\rho_d V_d(\xi)} \quad (\text{S.17})$$

Gas volume fraction:

$$\alpha_d(t) = \int_{\xi_{min}}^{\xi_{max}} \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\rho_d(t)} d\xi \quad (\text{S.18})$$

Interfacial area density:

$$a = \pi \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^2 f_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi \quad (\text{S.19})$$

Sauter mean diameter:

$$\xi_{32} = \frac{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^3 f_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi}{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^2 f_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi} \quad (\text{S.20})$$

S.2.3. Applied Parameters in the Simulations

The following tables summarize the parameters used in the simulations.

Table S.1.: Applied parameters in the comparison of numerical solution methods. Analytical solution and model equations given in the reference below and Alzyod *et al.* [27].

Symbol	Values			
	<i>Case 1</i>	<i>Case 2</i>	<i>Case 3</i>	<i>Case 4</i>
ξ_{\min}	1	5×10^{-4}	0.01	2×10^{-6}
ξ_{\max}	180	2.0	2.0	1000×10^{-6}
N_{ξ}	100	100	100	200*
$N_{\xi, \text{int}}$			100	200*
t	(0,50)	(0,1)	(0,15)	(0,10)
(a, b, c)	(0.0, 1.0, 0.0)	(1.8, 0.0, 0.0)		
J	0	20	0	0
C_{bf}				10.2×10^8
C_{cf}				8×10^{-7}
Reference	[39]	[37]	[42]	[38]

* $N_{\xi}=80$, $N_{\xi, \text{int}}=100$ for OC

Table S.2.: Applied default parameters in the parameter studies.

<i>Property data</i>			<i>Process conditions</i>		
Symbol	Value	Unit	Symbol	Value	Unit
ρ_d	1.18	kg m^{-3}	ε	0.6	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
ρ_c	1000	kg m^{-3}	$\alpha_{d, \text{ini}}$	0.08	-
σ	72	mJ m^{-2}	$\dot{m}_{d, \text{in}}$	0.02	kg s^{-1}
μ_c	0.001	Pa s	Δw	-6×10^{-6}	kg kg^{-1}
k_{MT}	1×10^{-5}	m s^{-1}	J_d^m	0.0	kg m^{-3}
			<i>mod</i>	1	-
<i>Reator Geometry</i>			<i>Dispersed Phase</i>		
Symbol	Value	Unit	Symbol	Value	Unit
V_R	1.0	m^3	C_{cf}	1×10^{-3}	-
μ_0	200	μm	C_1	5×10^{12}	m^{-2}
σ_0	20	μm	C_{bf}	6×10^{-3}	-
	<i>Numerics</i>		C_2	1×10^{-5}	-
N_{ξ}	500		ξ_{\min}	2	μm
$N_{\xi, \text{int}}$	500		ξ_{\max}	1000	μm

Table S.3.: Varied and applied parameter ranges in the parameter studies.

Symbol	Min. Value	Max. Value	Unit
ε	0.1	5.0	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^3$
$\alpha_{d,\text{ini}}$	0.01	0.3	-
$\dot{m}_{d,\text{in}}$	0.01	0.1	kg s^{-1}
k_{MT}	1×10^{-8}	1×10^{-4}	m s^{-1}
k_{MT}	-1×10^{-8}	-2×10^{-4}	m s^{-1}
μ_0	150	900	μm
σ_0	4	37	μm
μ_1	120	800	μm^*
μ_c	0.2×10^{-3}	1.5	Pa s
σ	17	85	mJ m^{-2}
ρ_c	600	5000	kg m^{-3}
ρ_d	0.1	6	kg m^{-3}
C_{bf}	5×10^{-5}	0.5	-
C_{cf}	3×10^{-5}	0.013	-

* $\text{mod} = 2$

Table S.4.: Applied parameters in the model application.

<i>Property data</i>			<i>Process conditions</i>		
Symbol	Value	Unit	Symbol	Value	Unit
ρ_d	1.2	kg m^{-3}	ε	0.156	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
ρ_c	1000	kg m^{-3}	$\alpha_{d,\text{ini}}$	0.06	-
σ	72	mJ m^{-2}	$\dot{m}_{d,\text{in}}$	0.055	g s^{-1}
μ_c	1.0	mPa s	Δw	0	kg kg^{-1}
μ_d	0.18	mPa s	J_d^{m}	0	kg m^{-3}
$w_{c,\text{EtOH}}$	0.01	kg kg^{-1}			

<i>Reator Geometry</i>			<i>Dispersed Phase</i>		
Symbol	Value	Unit	Symbol	Value	Unit
V_R	0.027	m^3	C_{cf}	1.89×10^{-6}	-
d_R	0.3	m	C_1	4.28×10^{11}	m^{-2}
			C_{bf}	6.24×10^{-3}	-
			C_2	5.00×10^{-6}	-
			ξ_{min}	1	μm
			ξ_{max}	2000	μm

<i>Numerics</i>		
N_ξ	400	
$N_{\xi,\text{int}}$	400	

S.3. Model Derivations

S.3.1. Derivation of the Outlet Mass Flow Rate

To derive an expression for \dot{m}_{out} , the assumption that the reactor volume V_R is constant and does not move is used (the substantial derivative reduces to a partial derivative). Furthermore, the reactor volume

can be represented as the sum of the enclosed fluids. So it follows:

$$\frac{dV_R}{dt} = \frac{\partial V_R}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{S.21})$$

$$= \frac{\partial V_d}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial V_c}{\partial t} \quad (\text{S.22})$$

The liquid phase can generally be regarded as incompressible, from which follows $\frac{\partial V_c}{\partial t} = 0$. If this is used

$$\frac{\partial V_d}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{S.23})$$

$$\hat{=} \frac{\partial \alpha_d}{\partial t} \quad (\text{S.24})$$

it can be concluded that the volume of the dispersed phase in the reactor is always constant respectively the gas holdup. If the definition of mass density and the chain rule are applied to Eq. (S.23) we get:

$$\frac{\partial V_d}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{m_d}{\rho_d} \right) \quad (\text{S.25})$$

$$= \frac{1}{\rho_d} \frac{\partial m_d}{\partial t} - \frac{m_d}{\rho_d^2} \frac{\partial \rho_d}{\partial t} \quad (\text{S.26})$$

Now an expression for the total mass of the dispersed phase (m_d) follows from a simple mass balance.

$$\frac{\partial m_d}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}_r m_d) = \Gamma_d V_R \quad (\text{S.27})$$

Where Γ_d is the mass transfer rate per volume due to phase change and where $m_d = \rho_d \alpha_d V_R$ and constant V_R was used. If the Eq. (S.27) integrated and divided over/by the reactor volume it follows:

$$\dot{m}_d + \dot{m}_{d,\text{out}} - \dot{m}_{d,\text{in}} = \Gamma_d V_R \quad (\text{S.28})$$

where $\frac{\partial m_d}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_d$ and $\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}} = A_R/V_R v_{r,\text{out}} m_{d,\text{out}}$ was used. If Eq. (S.28) is inserted into Eq. (S.26) and converted to $\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}$ using Eq. (S.23), we obtain:

$$\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}} = \dot{m}_{d,\text{in}} + \Gamma_d V_R - \frac{m_d}{\rho_d} \frac{\partial \rho_d}{\partial t} \quad (\text{S.29})$$

The term before the temporal mass density changes can be converted to $\alpha_d V_R$ by applying the definition of the mass density and the gas volume fraction. The mass transfer rate Γ_d can be determined as the sum over the change in mass of the individual bubbles. Instead of summing over the individual bubbles, it can also be integrated over the BSD distribution. Since nucleation occurs in the system, this is taken into account as an additional term.

$$\Gamma_d = \sum_i \frac{1}{V_R} \frac{dm_d}{dt} + J_d^m \quad (\text{S.30})$$

$$= \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^n(\xi, t) \frac{dm_d}{dt} d\xi + J_d^m \quad (\text{S.31})$$

Finally, if the number based BSD $f_d^n(\xi, t)$ is converted into a mass-based one with the formula Eq. (S.17), Eq. (S.16) follows.

S.3.2. Simplification of the Generalized PBE to STR Application

Instead of simplifying the very lengthy KTAWSR [14], we start from a generalized PBE. However, the result is the same. Starting from a generalized PBE [26] with 1D particle size property space we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \\ &= \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{V(\xi)} \frac{1}{\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{dm_d}{dt} - B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.32})$$

If the Eq. (S.32) is averaged over the reactor volume, which means integrated and divided by the averaging volume, the reactor volume, and Gauss' theorem is applied to the convection term in physical space, the following results:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{V_R} \int_{V_R} \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} dV + \frac{1}{V_R} \int_{\delta V_R} (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \cdot d\mathbf{A} + \frac{1}{V_R} \int_{V_R} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) dV \\ &= \frac{1}{V_R} \int_{V_R} \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{V(\xi)} \frac{1}{\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{dm_d}{dt} - B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) dV \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.33})$$

Strictly speaking, this corresponds to volume averaging, and the volume averaging theorems [97] should be applied. Next, the averages of products would have to be related to products of averages. This results in new unclosed terms that either have to be described or neglected. We abbreviate these steps for the sake of brevity and assume that the values within the volume integrals do not depend on the location, so that these can be omitted. Furthermore, we refrain from labeling these now volume-averaged values separately. It follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{V_R} \int_{\delta V_R} (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \cdot d\mathbf{A} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}(\xi, t) f_d^m(\xi, t)) \\ &= \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{V(\xi)} \frac{1}{\rho_d(\xi, t)} \frac{dm_d}{dt} - B_D^m(\xi, t) + B_B^m(\xi, t) - C_D^m(\xi, t) + C_B^m(\xi, t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.34})$$

Only the second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (S.34) needs to be further processed. Since the boundary area δV_R of V_R is only permeable on two surfaces, the inlet and the outlet, this surface integral breaks down into two parts. Taking into account the surface normal of the surface element and assuming that the values within the integral are constant on the respective surface resp. we do the same trick as before with now area averaging, we get:

$$\frac{1}{V_R} \int_{\delta V_R} (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \cdot d\mathbf{A} = \frac{A_{\text{out}}}{V_R} v_{r,\text{out}}(\xi, t) f_{d,\text{out}}^m(\xi, t) - \frac{A_{\text{in}}}{V_R} v_{r,\text{in}}(\xi, t) f_{d,\text{in}}^m(\xi, t) \quad (\text{S.35})$$

The inlet distribution $f_{d,\text{in}}^m(\xi, t)$ is assumed to be known. Due to the ideal mixed assumption, $f_{d,\text{out}}^m(\xi, t) = f_d^m(\xi, t)$ follows. The terms preceding the distribution functions can now be converted into a volume flow rate by expanding them by the gas volume fraction and into a mass flow rate by further expanding them by the mass density. This results in the following expression for the outlet term:

$$\frac{A_{\text{out}}}{V_R} v_{r,\text{out}}(\xi, t) f_{d,\text{out}}^m(\xi, t) = \frac{A_{\text{out}} \alpha_d(t) v_{r,\text{out}}(\xi, t)}{V_R \alpha_d(t)} f_d^m(\xi, t) = \frac{\dot{V}_{d,\text{out}}(\xi, t)}{V_R \alpha_d(t)} f_d^m(\xi, t) \quad (\text{S.36})$$

$$= \frac{\dot{V}_{d,\text{out}}(\xi, t) \rho_d(\xi, t)}{V_R \alpha_d(t) \rho_d(\xi, t)} f_d^m(\xi, t) = \frac{\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}(\xi, t) \rho_d(\xi, t)}{V_R \alpha_d(t)} f_d^m(\xi, t) \quad (\text{S.37})$$

If the Eq. (S.18) is employed to calculate the gas volume fraction from the mass density function, the Eq. (S.37) could be further simplified to:

$$\frac{\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}(\xi, t) \rho_d(\xi, t)}{V_R \alpha_d} f_d^m(\xi, t) = \frac{\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}(\xi, t)}{V_R} \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^m(\xi, t) d\xi} \quad (\text{S.38})$$

$$\approx \frac{\dot{m}_{d,\text{out}}(t)}{V_R} \frac{f_d^m(\xi, t)}{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^m(\xi, t) d\xi} \quad (\text{S.39})$$

The inlet flow term follows analogously. This means that only the size-dependent mass or volume flow rate of the gas phase at inlet and outlet remain unknown (cf. Eq. (S.38)). These flow rates could now be determined using experimental results or an additional model. For the sake of simplicity, however, we assume that the in- and outlet mass or volume flow rate is independent of the bubble size, which corresponds to the assumption that all bubbles have the same effective velocity or residence time resulting in the finale Eq. (S.39).

S.3.3. Conversion Rules for Comparison Experiment and Simulation

In order to use experimentally measured BSD $\hat{f}_{d,\text{exp}}^n$ for the simulation, e.g. as initial distribution, it must be converted into a number or mass density function. Since the experimentally measured BSD represents a normalized distribution without information on how many bubbles or how much dispersed phase mass is in the system, further information is needed to represent this, the gas holdup provides this information. In order to use this, we derive the necessary equation below.

Starting from the definition of the normalized number density distribution Eq. (S.40).

$$\hat{f}_d^n(\xi, t) = \frac{f_d^n(\xi, t)}{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi} \quad (\text{S.40})$$

$$= \frac{f_d^n(\xi, t)}{n_d(t)} \quad (\text{S.41})$$

where the definition of the number density or the number of particles per volume $n_d(t) = \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi$ was used. The definition of the gas volume fraction Eq. (S.42) is used to determine the number density.

$$\alpha_d = n_d \bar{V}_\xi \quad (\text{S.42})$$

This is obtained from the product of the n_d number density and the mean bubble volume \bar{V}_ξ . The mean bubble volume can be calculated on the basis of Eq. (S.43), which only requires a normalized distribution.

$$\bar{V}_\xi = \frac{\pi}{6} \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^3 \hat{f}_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi \quad (\text{S.43})$$

If the Eq. (S.43), Eq. (S.42) and Eq. (S.41) are inserted into each other, the conversion rule follows:

$$f_d^n = \hat{f}_d^n \frac{\alpha_d}{\frac{\pi}{6} \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^3 \hat{f}_d^n(\xi, t) d\xi} \quad (\text{S.44})$$

Here \hat{f}_d^n could be an experimental BSD. The conversion to a mass density function is then carried out using Eq. (S.17). The other way around is simply accomplished by using Eq. (S.40).

S.4. Finite Volume Method with Gauss Quadrature – FVMG

S.4.1. Grid points

A cell-centered equidistant grid with a cell width of $\Delta\xi$ according to Eq.(S.46) is used.

$$\Delta\xi = \frac{\xi_{\max} - \xi_{\min}}{N_\xi} \quad (\text{S.45})$$

$$\xi \in \xi_{\min} + \frac{2i-1}{2}\Delta\xi \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N_\xi \quad (\text{S.46})$$

The function `range(start, stop, length)` from `Base.jl` was used to calculate the grid points.

S.4.2. Convection

A high-resolution scheme with a flux limiter was used to discretize the convection term in property space, see Eq. (S.47) and following. An application to the convection term in physical space should also be possible, perhaps with a different flux limiter. In this work we used a monotonic upstream-centered scheme for conservation laws (MUSCL) according to van Leer [98] scheme which is total variation diminishing. Based on the slope, which is determined by the smoothness indicator Eq. (S.49), a high resolution scheme switches to a non oscillating low order scheme, e.g. first order upwind, in areas with a large slope, e.g. around discontinuities, and to an more accurate higher order scheme with less numerical diffusion, e.g. central scheme, in areas with a small slope (smooth areas). The extent to which the two methods, lower and higher order, are "mixed" is determined by the flux limiter Eq. (S.50). The MUSCL scheme according to [98] is summarized below with a flux limiter according to van Leer [99].

$$\frac{\partial(v_\xi(\xi_i)f(\xi_i))}{\partial\xi} \approx \frac{1}{\Delta\xi_i} (F_{i+1/2} - F_{i-1/2}) \quad (\text{S.47})$$

$$F_i = v_\xi(\xi_i)f(\xi_i) \quad (\text{S.48})$$

$$s_i = \frac{F_i - F_{i-1} + \epsilon}{F_{i+1} - F_i + \epsilon} \quad (\text{S.49})$$

$$\Phi(s_i) = \frac{|s_i| + s_i}{1 + |s_i|} \quad (\text{S.50})$$

$$v_\xi(\xi_i) > 0$$

$$F_{i+1/2} = F_i + \frac{1}{2}\Phi(s_i)(F_{i+1} - F_i) \quad (\text{S.51})$$

$$F_{i-1/2} = F_{i-1} + \frac{1}{2}\Phi(s_{i-1})(F_i - F_{i-1}) \quad (\text{S.52})$$

$$v_\xi(\xi_i) < 0$$

$$F_{i+1/2} = F_{i+1} + \frac{1}{2}\Phi(s_{i+1})(F_{i+2} - F_{i+1}) \quad (\text{S.53})$$

$$F_{i-1/2} = F_i + \frac{1}{2}\Phi(s_i)(F_{i-1} - F_i) \quad (\text{S.54})$$

$$(\text{S.55})$$

Where ϵ was added to the smoothness indicator Eq. (S.49) to avoid diving by zero, $\epsilon = 1 \times 10^{-32}$. The above scheme is not applicable for the first two and the last cell nodes resp. the last two and the the first (depending on the sign of v_ξ), otherwise ghost points would have to be introduced, instead a first order upwind scheme is used.

$v_\xi(\xi_i) > 0$

$$\frac{\partial (v_\xi(\xi_1)f(\xi_1))}{\partial \xi} \approx \frac{1}{\Delta \xi_1} (F_1 - F_0) \quad (\text{S.56})$$

$$\frac{\partial (v_\xi(\xi_2)f(\xi_2))}{\partial \xi} \approx \frac{1}{\Delta \xi_2} (F_{1-1/2} - F_1) \quad (\text{S.57})$$

$$\frac{\partial (v_\xi(\xi_{N_\xi})f(\xi_{N_\xi}))}{\partial \xi} \approx \frac{-F_{N_\xi+1/2}}{\Delta \xi_{N_\xi}} \quad (\text{S.58})$$

$v_\xi(\xi_i) < 0$

$$\frac{\partial (v_\xi(\xi_1)f(\xi_1))}{\partial \xi} \approx \frac{1}{\Delta \xi_1} (F_{1-1/2} + F_0) \quad (\text{S.59})$$

$$\frac{\partial (v_\xi(\xi_{N_\xi-1})f(\xi_{N_\xi-1}))}{\partial \xi} \approx \frac{1}{\Delta \xi_2} (F_{N_\xi} - F_{1+1/2}) \quad (\text{S.60})$$

$$\frac{\partial (v_\xi(\xi_{N_\xi})f(\xi_{N_\xi}))}{\partial \xi} \approx \frac{-F_{N_\xi}}{\Delta \xi_{N_\xi}} \quad (\text{S.61})$$

Where F_0 is a boundary flux i.e. the nucleation rate.

S.4.3. Interpolation

In this work we used piece-wise cubic Hermite spline interpolation [54] because it preserves the monotonicity (i.e. it will not under- or overshoot). The scheme is summarized in Eq. (S.62) - Eq. (S.68) where a three point finite difference scheme was used in order to determine the slope g_i .

$$f(\xi) \approx \psi_{00}(\xi')\xi_i f_i + \psi_{10}(\xi')(\xi_{i+1} - \xi_i)s_i + \psi_{01}(\xi')f_{\xi+1} + \psi_{11}(\xi')(\xi_{i+1} - \xi_i)s_{i+1} \quad (\text{S.62})$$

$$\psi_{00}(\xi') = (1 + 2\xi')(1 - \xi')^2 \quad (\text{S.63})$$

$$\psi_{10}(\xi') = \xi'(1 - \xi')^2 \quad (\text{S.64})$$

$$\psi_{01}(\xi') = \xi'^2(3 - 2\xi') \quad (\text{S.65})$$

$$\psi_{11}(\xi') = \xi'^2(\xi' - 1) \quad (\text{S.66})$$

$$\xi' = \frac{\xi - \xi_i}{\xi_{i+1} - \xi_i} \quad (\text{S.67})$$

$$g_i = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{f_{i+1} - f_i}{\xi_{i+1} - \xi_i} + \frac{f_i - f_{i-1}}{\xi_i - \xi_{i-1}} \right) \quad (\text{S.68})$$

Instead of an own implementation the package `PCHIPInterpolation.jl` was used. Due to the fact that a cell center scheme was used but the breakage and coalescence spans the entire domain including the boundary points, it is necessary to extrapolate towards them. To accomplish this, a constant slope based on linear interpolation was assumed wherefore the package `Interpolations.jl` was used.

S.4.4. Gauss Quadrature

For the approximation of integrals a Gauss quadrature rule [52] was used which is defined on a limited interval $[-1,1]$, e.g. Gauss-Legendre or Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto. The only difference between these two is that Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto includes the boundary points $-1,1$ and Gauss-Legendre does not. Gauss-Legendre was used in this work, as the boundary values in the coalescence birth term assume very large values that are difficult to integrate. Eq. (S.69) shows the integration rule, where the standard interval $[-1,1]$ has already been transformed to an arbitrary $[\xi_{\min}, \xi_{\max}]$ interval (indicated with *) using Eq. (S.70)

and Eq. (S.71). The nodes $\tilde{\xi}_i$ and weights $\tilde{\omega}_i$ on the interval $[-1,1]$ were calculated with the function `gausslegendre($N_{\xi,\text{int}}$)` from the packet `FastGaussQuadrature.jl`.

$$\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f(\xi) d\xi \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\xi,\text{int}}} f(\xi_i^*) \omega_i^* \quad (\text{S.69})$$

$$\tilde{\xi}_i^* = \frac{\xi_{\max} - \xi_{\min}}{2} \tilde{\xi}_i + \frac{\xi_{\max} + \xi_{\min}}{2} \quad (\text{S.70})$$

$$\tilde{\omega}_i^* = \frac{\xi_{\max} - \xi_{\min}}{2} \tilde{\omega}_i \quad (\text{S.71})$$

S.5. Used Packages and Version

The programming language Julia [55] in the Version 1.10 was used to implement the MPB. The `DifferentialEquations.jl` package with the algorithm `CVODE_BDF(linear_solver = :GMRES)` from the `Sundials.jl` [100, 101] package was used for solving the system of ODEs. In order to calculate a steady-state solution the functionality of the `DifferentialEquations.jl` package was used. There a transient problem can be transformed into a steady-state problem using the same algorithm as before within the steady-state algorithm `DynamicSS()` with $abstol = 10^{-4}$, $reltol = 10^{-3}$, $dt_{\text{ini}} = 10^{-6}$. Higher accuracies were also possible but slowed down the calculation considerably without any significant change in the result.

The package `Optimization.jl` [102] in the Version 3.19.3 offers a unified interface to formulate optimization problems and integrates various optimization libraries. `SciMLSensitivity.jl`, in the Version 7.51.0 enables rapid derivative calculations through automatic differentiation and serves as a comprehensive ecosystem for scientific machine learning [103]. The LBFGS and Nelder-Mead algorithms are provided in the `Optim.jl` package in the version 1.9.2 [104]. In the case of the parameter estimation procedure the number of grid and intergration points were reduced to $N_{\xi} = 100$ and $N_{\xi,\text{int}} = 100$, due to computational time. In addition, the algorithm for solving the systems of ODEs was chosen automatically by the package `DifferentialEquations.jl`, as `CVODE_BDF` algorithm with the linear `solver=:GMRES` is not compatible with the parameter estimation procedure. It is important to mention that the NaN safemode feature of the `ForwardDiff.jl` package (included in `SciMLSensitivity.jl`) was enabled to prevent the optimization procedure from halting when NaN values arise when the step sizes becomes very small.

Tab. S.5 summarizes all used packages within the programming language Julia including the Version number.

Table S.5.: Used packages in the programming language Julia.

Package	Version
CSV	v0.10.13
DataFrames	v1.6.1
DelimitedFiles	v1.9.1
DifferentialEquations	v7.11.0
FastGaussQuadrature	v1.0.2
Interpolations	v0.15.1
NLSolve	v4.5.1
NumericalIntegration	v0.2.0
Optim	v1.9.2
OptimizationOptimJL	v0.1.14
Optimization	v3.19.3
PCHIPInterpolation	v0.2.0
Plots	v1.40.1
Preferences	v1.4.3
Revise	v3.5.14
SciMLSensitivity	v7.51.0
SpecialFunctions	v2.3.1
SpecialPolynomials	v0.4.9
StatsFuns	v1.3.1
Sundials	v4.24.0
XLSX	v0.10.1

S.6. Geometric Dimension of STR Used in the Experiments

Table S.6.: Summary of the geometric dimension of the STR used in the experiments.

Quantity	Value	Unit
Diameter	300	mm
Height	940	mm
Baffle plate thickness	44	mm
Length baffle plate	838	mm
Length stirrer shaft	900	mm
Diameter stirrer shaft	20	mm
Spacing between turbines	140	mm
Stirrer diameter	100	mm
Turbine blade height	20	mm
Turbine blade width	25	mm

S.7. Additional Figures

Figure S.4.: Mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for different property data: (A) - viscosity of the continuous phase μ_c , (B) - surface tension σ , (C) - mass density of the continuous phase ρ_c , (D) mass density of the dispersed phase ρ_d .

Figure S.5.: Mass density function f_d^m as a function of bubble size ξ for different (A) - gas fluxes j_d and (B) - energy dissipation rates ϵ for the case with constant gas holdup.